

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijdrCo-creating solutions for Disaster Risk Reduction in multi-country research projects – Opportunities and Challenges[☆]Maike Vollmer^{a,*}, Claudia Berchtold^a, Jeannette Anniés^b^a Fraunhofer Institute for Technological Trend Analysis – INT, Euskirchen, Germany^b Institute for Human Factors and Technology Management – IAT, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Co-creation
 Disaster risk reduction
 Resilience
 Citizen engagement
 EU projects

ABSTRACT

Enhancing Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) in a comprehensive and efficient manner requires consideration of needs of diverse stakeholders. Co-creation intends to involve all pertinent stakeholders, from the identification of needs through to the development and finally implementation of suitable solutions. However, challenges exist in multi-country projects that may hamper the implementation of co-creation. This article explores opportunities and challenges associated with co-creation in EU projects in DRR. It builds on literature mainly of applied science and draws upon insights gained from two EU Horizon 2020 projects: RiskPACC, which developed and implemented a co-creation approach to better understand different risk perceptions and to foster two-way communication among citizens and civil protection authorities, and Firelogue, which in applying a co-creation approach, aimed to explore the design of integrated wildfire risk management approaches under consideration of justice aspects. Opportunities of co-creation include fostering mutual understanding, matching needs with possible solutions, and involving all relevant stakeholders. Challenges include mutual understanding among diverse participants, time and resources, (continuous) involvement of all relevant stakeholders, equitable distribution of power to justly recognize different interests, and required skills in co-creation. In addition, specific considerations in relation to characteristics of EU projects involving multiple countries concern challenges of language, funding conditions, the possibly higher number of stakeholders, and questions of representativeness. Co-developed solutions within a project are at risk not to be implemented after the project. However, the facilitation of networking and establishing relationships present an advantage of co-creation that is possibly supported within large interdisciplinary and multi-country projects.

1. Introduction

Co-creation has increasingly emerged as a concept to address challenges in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR). While traditional approaches in DRR have been rather organized top-down, the need to collaborate with a broad range of stakeholders that play a role in

This article is part of a special issue entitled: RiskPACC Engaging Society published in International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction.[☆] This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019707 (RiskPACC) and grant agreement No. 101036534 (Firelogue).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: maike.vollmer@int.fraunhofer.de (M. Vollmer), claudia.berchtold@int.fraunhofer.de (C. Berchtold), jeannette.annies@iat.uni-stuttgart.de (J. Anniés).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2025.105187>

Received 9 August 2024; Received in revised form 2 January 2025; Accepted 6 January 2025

Available online 7 January 2025

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DRR, both from the “demand/need” and the “supply” side, has become clearer over the past decades, including the collaboration between researchers and practitioners [1]. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction points out that

“There is a need for the public and private sectors and civil society organizations, as well as academia and scientific and research institutions, to work more closely together and to create opportunities for collaboration, and for businesses to integrate disaster risk into their management practices.” [2, p. 10]

Co-creation and related terms such as design thinking are loosely defined terms of innovative processes. While design thinking can be understood as a process or thinking culture, co-creation is one of the adaptations that is more precise on the stakeholders that are part of the process (e.g. [3]) establishing a success criterion of engaging new audiences [4]. It equips design thinking with core values such as representation and participation. Within design thinking and co-creation processes, new technologies, for example information and communications technology (ICT), may be developed. The co-creational aspect of its development aspires to help make a new technology innovative and disruptive through the collaboration of previously separated interest groups [5–7].

While concepts of co-creation are increasingly adapted in DRR and in the context of climate change research [1,5], e. g., their operationalization is not yet well researched [6]. Co-creation in DRR has in many cases emerged based on the objective of leveraging local knowledge owned by citizens. Frequently, respective approaches are hence applied to rather local DRR measures or strategies such as site-specific risk management strategies¹, targeted solutions such as early-warning systems² or risk information systems.³ The recognition of different needs, perceptions, and types of knowledge among different groups of citizens relevant for DRR, including marginalized or vulnerable groups, has led to the ambition of involving all these diverse groups. However, depending on the context and specific goal, co-creation approaches can also focus, for example, on employees of organizations involved in DRR.

Depending on the setting, participants need to be carefully defined and selected based on the specific context and objective. Ideally, the selected stakeholders reflect a good representation of actual user types including marginalized and vulnerable groups. However, on the practical side, there can be limitations to an ideal setting. This article hence addresses some of the challenges that can arise in applying co-creation approaches within multi-country collaborative research projects, making use of two examples. In the recently closed RiskPACC project⁴ that targeted better understanding of different risk perceptions and fostering two-way communication among citizens and civil protection authorities (CPAs), crucial participants were CPAs, citizens, specific vulnerable groups, researchers and technology providers. In contrast, the Firelogue project⁵ aimed to explore the design of integrated fire management approaches under consideration of justice aspects. Thus, crucial co-creators in Firelogue have been policy-makers and stakeholders active in wildfire risk management (WFRM).

In the present work, we derive and elaborate on general opportunities and challenges of co-creation approaches as depicted in the literature of mainly applied science, and relate them to specific challenges and opportunities when applied to the two exemplary EU-scale research projects. Further, we discuss possible countermeasures to address the challenges. In these two EU Horizon2020 projects, we enacted as project coordinators and/or work package leader. In both projects, we created and initialized the co-creation processes, took part in the execution of the co-creation activities such as workshops, and closely monitored them. Therefore, this work mainly presents which opportunities and challenges we found from this hands-on experience in applied science, compared to literature findings, and how the projects respectively tackled the challenges found.

2. Co-creation in disaster risk reduction

2.1. System thinking and collaborative governance

Conventional risk governance approaches have tended to be based on well-established cause-and-effect-relationships. In other words, authorities developed risk assessments including different types of hazards and related scenarios which built the basis for risk management measures including prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery. By contrast, systemic risk governance tends to emphasize the complex causal structures related, for example, to climate change adaptation and mitigation, land-use changes, consumption patterns, etc., often with feedback mechanisms marked by uncertainties and including the potential for cascading or compounding events potentially leading to failure of the whole system. Barry Richmond [7] already wrote in 1990 that the problems in the world are growing more intractable and are becoming increasingly resistant to unilateral solutions. Richmond concluded that thinking in systems was an important part of an effective strategy for developing capacities for these challenges (ibid.). Focusing on systemic risks, the 2019 Global Assessment Report (GAR) acknowledged that such risks also require for new forms of *systemic governance* considering “the interconnected elements and interdependencies among individual risks” [8, p. 54]. System thinking hence requires us to see the bigger picture – from which one may identify multiple leverage points to support constructive change. It offers a pathway to identify improved policy solutions for complex and multi-objective policy issues.

¹ Instant Flood Risk Modelling (Inform) Tool for Co-Design of Flood Risk Management Strategies with Stakeholders in Can Tho City, Vietnam.

² E.g. Community-Level, Participatory Co-Design for Landslide Warning with Implications for Climate Services. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/5/4294>.

³ Co-creation of urban hazard, vulnerability and risk information system towards sustainable regional development trajectories in Sulawesi, Indonesia, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06234-0>.

⁴ EU H2020 project RiskPACC – Risk Perception and Action to enhance Civil Protection-Citizen Interaction (09/2021-08/2024).

⁵ EU H2020 project Firelogue – Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management (11/2021-10/2025).

However, systems thinking – to facilitate transformative change – needs to be translated into governance regimes to understand the drivers and interrelations of risks and to exploit systems methodologies in designing and implementing robust, holistic, and transformative adaptation strategies [9]. In other words, taking complexities and interrelations of managing risk into consideration, requires for specific policy processes, or risk governance. In contrast to conventional top-down approaches, policymaking (in the European Union) typically involves a broad network of government, market and civil society actors across sectors and scales. Polycentric government structures (i.e. novel arrangements across sectors and scales) as well as inclusive stakeholder collaboration – collaborative governance – are increasingly considered essential for co-designing and implementing robust and integrated risk management policies. Collaborative governance can be defined as

“The processes and structures of public policy decision making and management that engage people constructively across the boundaries of public agencies, levels of government, and/or the public, private and civic spheres in order to carry out a public purpose that could not otherwise be accomplished.” [10, p. 2]

2.2. From top-down to co-created solutions in disaster risk reduction

Closely related to the transition from conventional risk governance to system thinking and collaborative governance, is a transition from top-down to co-creation approaches and design thinking in innovation processes. Design thinking “originated from processes used by designers” [11, p. 727], yet progressed to an iterative process of problem-solving and decision-making, implementing a participative approach. In sum, it became a “user-centric innovation method[] [...] with accompanying mindsets and toolkits” [11, p. 727]. Based on the design thinking environment are different creational and creative techniques, methods, or tools – such as co-creation. Co-creation is a process of creation [12] that aspires to increase the levels of co-operation and collaboration between different stakeholders that are relevant to a certain decision-making process. By including transdisciplinary stakeholders [3] in co-creation, one of the main goals is to enhance the acceptance [13] of the decision made for the broader society where it is later implemented.

In many cases (but not all), co-creation aims at involving citizen’s knowledge, perspectives, and needs in an innovation process. The aspiration of involving citizens in this process shows how vital the stakeholders are, especially as soon as there is a (political) decision-making process involved that has far-reaching consequences. Involvement in decision-making processes will lead to a greater “consent of citizens to government activities” [14, p. 677]. Due to the element of civic engagement, co-creation needs to be linked back to paradigms in political sciences. Comparing it to collaborative governance, e. g., shows how co-creation can be interpreted as a democratic, deliberative format [15], which engages citizens in “consensus-oriented decision making” [9, p. 543]. To establish a successful process of consensus-building, a co-creation activity would have to provide the space for “dialogue where all are heard, respected, and equally able to participate” [16, p. 35]. As a result, both the notion to give stakeholders an equal voice, as well as considering a two-way communication flow [17], are core values to co-creation. Likewise, citizens should be given the authority to enforce the decisions made in participative processes [18]. Otherwise, the prospect of civic engagement is only tokenism [18], which can in turn deeply disappoint and frustrate participants [19,20]. Since one of the goals is to co-create solutions that may find their way into policies and governance, the stakeholder group should represent the population that the decision made will be effective for. In a co-creation workshop, the group members are representing a certain social role such as, e.g., citizen or first responder. The participants will bring their own point of view to the table and can therefore represent only themselves or others with the same characteristics [21]. All in all, a diverse group of participants is needed because hazards affect population groups very differently, as, for example, women and girls, and men and boys [22]. Objectives of co-creation in DRR hence include better understanding the needs of citizens, which can differ essentially, better match supplied DRR actions to the “real” demands, and develop solutions that are relevant to the specific society and that are in fact useable in practice, while at the same time ensuring scientific quality [1,6]. Implemented appropriately, co-creation can help to avoid mutual misunderstandings and support aligning scientific and practical perceptions [1]. Thus, innovations coming out of a co-creation process have the potential of showing the desired disruptiveness, as well as enhance disaster resilience. By taking the political aspects into account, policies and other solutions found in co-creation processes involving a diverse group of stakeholders may close a gap in reaching “practitioners on the ground or political actors at the decision-making level” [23, p. 1].

The urgent need for enhanced collaboration among the different players in DRR has also emerged from research on pertinent policy frameworks. The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction not only points out the need for strengthened collaboration among sectors, civil society and academia, but explicitly requires states to encourage civil society, volunteers, organized voluntary work organizations, and community-based organizations to provide specific knowledge and pragmatic guidance managing disaster risk [2]. At the same time, interaction between policy makers, scientists and citizens is still a shortfall, and policy implementation is still poor [24, p. 1].

The “Quadruple Helix Model”, a conceptual framework for fostering innovation introduced by Carayannis & Campbell [25], assumes four main actors in innovation processes: academia/universities, industry, state/government, and civil society [25,26]. By adding the perspective of civil society, it extends the “Triple Helix” introduced by Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff [27], which focuses on the academia/universities-industry-state/government interrelations. The Quadruple Helix Model thus highlights the importance of considering societal needs and values, and promotes co-creation and participatory methods [25].

As further explained in the following chapter, the actors involved in the RiskPACC co-creation approach very much correspond to the four actors of this model: academic entities led the development of the co-creation approach, facilitated its implementation, and co-developed technological and conceptual innovations. Companies brought in their technological expertise and co-developed

technological innovations. State/government organizations were involved especially via representatives of public disaster management organizations/departments, and the civil society was involved by including citizens and civil society organizations.

Similarly, the co-creation of policy recommendations in Firelogue was conceptually initiated and conceptualized by academia. A broad range of stakeholders was engaged in the development of the working groups and participation in the drafting of ideas through workshop formats. These included civil society organizations and NGOs as well as civil protection representatives and industry such as critical infrastructure operators and insurances. All of them participated actively in the workshops and complementary webinars. Both, workshop results and webinars created the knowledge base for drafting thematic recommendations at European scale.

2.3. Leading questions

By analyzing the implementation of co-creation approaches in two EU H2020 projects in the field of Disaster Risk Reduction, i. e., in the RiskPACC and Firelogue projects, we seek answers to the following questions.

- (a) In how far were the opportunities and challenges identified in previous studies confirmed in RiskPACC and Firelogue? In what way do they differ?
- (b) What are additional insights from applying co-creation approaches in RiskPACC and Firelogue? In how far are they related to characteristics of EU research projects involving multiple countries?

3. Co-creation in EU research projects

In this chapter, we will present the co-creation approaches as implemented in RiskPACC and in Firelogue. While the involved actors correspond to the four main actors of the Quadruple Helix Model of innovation, there is no final or singular design thinking or co-creation process, and the concept of co-creation has been adapted to the individual needs of each project. For RiskPACC and Firelogue, this resulted in the creation and initialization of two distinct, yet comparable co-creation approaches.

In chapter 4, we will then derive main opportunities and challenges of co-creation on DRR research, building on previous research on co-creation in the field of DRR. We reflect on opportunities and challenges from literature with the perspective of our experience in RiskPACC and Firelogue, and complement the results with additional insights and conclusions derived from applying co-creation in the two projects. Finally, we derive some recommendations on how to overcome challenges associated with co-creation in DRR (chapter 5).

3.1. The RiskPACC approach: enhancing civil protection-citizen interaction with co-creation workshops and co-design of ICTs

Enriching the traditional top-down approach in DRR with bottom-up communication, i. e., from citizens to Civil Protection Authorities (CPAs), was a main aim of the RiskPACC project. By enhancing communication in both directions, CPAs and citizens being both senders and receivers of communication, proper two-way communication can be established. In order to reach the goal of reducing communication gaps between CPAs and citizens, co-creation workshops have been put in place. In these workshops, facilitating exchange of perspectives and building trust between all parties stood in the foreground. Likewise, practical solutions to local problems were the focal point of the discussions. Moreover, four proposed technological solutions that had been pre-selected for the project (in their very initial stages), which had been matched with six case study areas, were iteratively tested and co-developed

Fig. 1. Adapted methodology for RISKPACC'S CO-CREATION LABS [28].

further.

3.1.1. Methodology

To explain the approach in further detail, general characteristics and model structures of co-creation processes have been tailored to the project's needs. The RiskPACC workshop structure has been set up as modular, so that it offered the workshop organizers and moderators the freedom and flexibility to make final adjustments to their specific needs [28, p. 52]. In brief, the workshop has been designed along the co-creation process phases Introduction, Conceptualization, Collaboration, and Continuation (ibid., see Fig. 1). The process itself has been developed further throughout the project as well, linking it to the RiskPACC Collaborative Framework (a conceptual and methodological guide facilitating collaboration between CPAs and citizens, entailing the four modules "Understanding", "Sharing", "Relating" and "Building") [29], and to allow case study leaders to select appropriate conceptual methodologies and approaches of co-designing technologies. In parallel, the content of the framework's modules has been iterated in two secluded sets of workshop phases and resulted in an adapted version [28,29].

According to the RiskPACC co-creation methodology, in a co-creation workshop conducted in a case study area selected for the RiskPACC project, firstly the DRR topic that was of highest relevance to the case study area was identified and *introduced*. Secondly, discussions on this specific topic facilitated an exchange of different understandings of risks, perspectives, and pertinent needs, fostering trust between the present participants, which were a diverse group of stakeholders in DRR including citizens and CPA representatives. Initial solutions that address the identified needs were *conceptualized*. Thirdly, these solutions were *collaborated* on further to develop simple prototypes. Alternatively, one of the four project's technological solutions was tested, and co-designed further. Lastly, the case study owners were advised to make sure the ideas and suggestions developed in the workshop as well as the relationships built can *continue* to exist in the future and be worked with/on, especially by follow-up communication among workshop facilitators and participants [28].

The co-creation process was implemented in two phases during the project. In the first phase, seven case study workshops were conducted in May 2022. The focus has been on the establishment of the network between civic and DRR representatives, to establish trust ties and social capital, and for the co-creation methodology to be tested and adapted (s. a.). In the second phase, each case study conducted at least two workshops in the time frame of January 2023–April 2023. Each technological tool has been tested twice in the workshops, with an intermediate improvement phase, leading to all of the tools reaching TRL5 or higher (s. Chapter 3.1.2).

Especially relevant to the *Conceptualization* phase is the implementation of dedicated conceptual tools and approaches. In RiskPACC, these conceptual tools were: storyboard user stories, the method of nudging, a risk communication exercise, and a simplified participatory mapping activity (s. b.). They have been highly relevant both in the case study workshops of the first phase (which was dedicated to prototyping solutions), as well as in those case study workshops of the second phase (which was dedicated to refining solutions), in cases where none of the four technological solutions was matched with the specific case study and thus the focus was on strategic or conceptual approaches.

A **storyboard user story** [28] is a method to simulate the implementation of a technological tool. It is written before the workshop/exchange with participants by looking at the functionalities of technological tools and writing a story about a (hazardous) situation in which it may be used. It is kept neutral and only describes the features of the tool. It is then evaluated by participants of a workshop to derive advantages and disadvantages of the concerned technological tool.

Nudging is a concept in behavioral sciences such as psychology or communication science. A nudge is an instrument to influence people's behavior without forbidding an option or forcing a change [30]. It can be used to persuade a person to behave in a socially desirable way. In RiskPACC, we considered nudging as an instrument integrated in a conceptual storyboard user story to be a good fit to give a technological solution an additional aspect [28].

The **risk communication exercise** [31] aimed to provide a flexible solution for case study partners to address their own specific context. The risk communication exercise has several overarching objectives, one of which is to enable CPAs to communicate an identified risk to citizens and to provide a structured space for dialogue to do so. Furthermore, the best forms of risk communication can be jointly identified, i.e. messages that are understandable, implementable, and actually help citizens in taking the appropriate risk reduction measures. Moreover, the exercise serves to support creating a trusting relationship.

Participatory mapping is mostly referred to the representations and visualization of spatial information that have been produced with the application of 'participatory' processes and with the direct involvement of community groups or individuals [32]. It is fundamentally established upon the ideas of dialogue and participation, while producing physical maps, or digital geospatial datasets generated by citizens, researchers, public authorities, and other interested parties through a process of participatory co-production [33].

3.1.2. Co-design of technological solutions

Within RiskPACC's six case studies, four ICT technologies have been co-designed, i. e., collaboratively developed further during the co-creation workshops. All technological solutions already had basic functionalities on Technology Readiness Level of TRL 2 or higher [34]. During RiskPACC, the ICTs have been improved to TRL 5/6.

One of the project's six case studies has iteratively tested an Augmented Reality (AR) application for the disaster types of floods and forest fires [35,36]. The **AEOLIAN** AR mobile application shows a novel approach to enable citizens (including volunteers) to communicate with CPAs during all phases of disaster risk management. This crowdsourcing solution enables a real-time bi-directional communication between its users and the relevant authorities. This tool has been co-designed during three rounds of targeted workshops with five organizations representing local authorities facing natural and anthropogenic hazards. In between the three rounds of testing, the tool has been improved from TRL 2 to TRL 6.

A second technology is a co-designed social network-like platform that aims at assisting communities with their disaster preparation and response [36]. The **HERMES** platform embodies a novel approach to educating citizens on different hazards and risk, allowing for communities of users with common interests to interact, as well as facilitating two-way communication between citizens and civil protection authorities. This tool has been co-designed and co-developed during three rounds of workshops with five local organizations working in various aspects of DRR. Following the co-creation process presented, the tool has been improved to TRL 5 [37].

Thirdly, **PublicSonar** uses artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing to analyse big data on social media websites to filter out relevant information in preparation to as well as during incidents. The tool has been tested and co-developed with four case studies in Europe during nine co-creation workshops. For testing, several functionalities such as the AI-supported sentiment analysis were available for CPAs to test. During the workshops, CPAs were asked to give feedback on the PublicSonar functionalities which improved the sentiment analysis functionality from a TRL 2/3 to TRL 5/6 [38].

Lastly, two RiskPACC-dashboards, **MappingDamage** and **ThermalComfortTracker**, have been set up on the GeoCitizen platform. The GeoCitizen platform is a merger of Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI) and Public Participatory GIS (PPGIS). MappingDamage, for example, was created as an application for disaster mapping, the channel customized especially to the needs of two European municipalities, and it remains open to collaboration with more local organizations. After the third round of RiskPACC workshops, MappingDamage has reached TRL 5 and may be improved further [39].

3.2. The Firelogue approach: governing complex risks through co-creation and consideration of justice aspects

Firelogue aimed at integrating wildfire risk management approaches, measures and stakeholders.⁶ It was built on the presupposition that wildfire risk and its management are characterised by complex interdependencies between human behaviour, socio-economic development and inequalities, climate, and the vegetation resources otherwise known as fuel (load) [40]. For example, unemployment, especially among young people, can lead to abandonment of traditionally cultivated landscapes and an increase in population size of cities, thereby on the one hand increasing fuel loads in the country and the extent of wildland-urban interfaces (WUI) on the other hand [41]. Similarly, different institutions and organizations may have diverging interests, needs, policies and practices. For example, “one division within a natural resource agency may aim to restore ecological conditions and processes on historically fire-prone forestlands while another division will aim to suppress fire on those same lands” [42]. In Europe however, traditional burning has ceased in many places [43], creating a paradox around the benefits of the use of fire and its impact of wildfires. In addition, responsibilities are not always aligned with the necessary resources. For example, Portuguese households sometimes lack the equipment to implement the preventive measures that they are entrusted with by law related to maintaining a clean perimeter around their houses [44]. Finally, Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) also encompasses redistributive aspects. For example, after the 2018 wildfires in Sweden, half of the burned area (6400 ha) mainly owned by small-scale private landowners was declared a nature reserve after the fire “with the state offering either economic compensation or a new forest property in the vicinity for those owning forest in the newly established nature reserve” [45].

The project hence also involved the different types of stakeholders according to the Quadruple Helix model, as mentioned above. However, the subject of the co-creation process were policy recommendations and hence governance aspects. It was presupposed that this requires for an additional systems thinking and collaborative governance approach in order to design holistic and coherent risk reduction strategies and to allow for the consideration of synergies and also conflicts between the relevant stakeholders. In addition, and in order to unveil matters of justice related to wildfire risk management in a multi-stakeholder setting, a particular focus was put on discussing different dimensions of justice.

3.2.1. Justice aspects

Firelogue has developed a conceptual framework that can build a ground for streamlining justice aspects into WFRM (see also [46]). Building on existing environmental, climate and disaster justice literature [47], it suggests that integrating aspects of justice with risk management concepts could add value for developing more integrated WFRM approaches by considering aspects of (social) vulnerability, intersectionality and stakeholder engagement more generally. The framework distinguishes three main dimensions of justice: 1) distributional justice (who should bear the costs and benefits of WFRM; how are hazard, exposure and vulnerability patterns distributed and who is responsible for their reduction); 2) procedural justice (does policy selection inclusively address stakeholder interests and inputs, either via institutional co-generation measures or ad hoc integration of views; which stakeholders are heard when developing WFRM policies and measures); 3) and restorative justice (how does the WFRM policy or measures address past or expected harms or wrongdoing; which restoration and compensation mechanisms, including insurance mechanisms, exist).

The latest policy frameworks such as the Landscape Fire Governance Framework [48] or the DG ECHO Peer Review Assessment Framework [49] continue to lack the important aspect of justice – although research related to aspects of vulnerability and justice have been conducted for decades in the wildfire risk domain. The Firelogue framework hence aimed to establish an analytical framework that allows stakeholders to comprehensively identify justice aspects across the whole risk management cycle by ensuring a whole of

⁶ Firelogue (Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management) was funded as a Coordination and Support Action under the European Green Deal “LC-GD-1-1-2020 - Preventing and fighting extreme wildfires with the integration and demonstration of innovative means” with the purpose to integrate and synthesise the results of three Innovation Actions funded under the same call with a volume of more than 60 Mio. € in research funding.

society approach.

3.2.2. Operationalising the Firelogue approach: working groups and workshops

The suggested approach was implemented by two main means: Working Groups and two workshops as detailed below.

3.2.2.1. Working groups. Firelogue clustered stakeholder interests along five thematic Working Groups (WGs): Environmental/Ecology WG, Societal WG, Infrastructure WG, Insurance WG and Civil protection WG. The WGs represent the main stakeholder groups playing a role in integrated wildfire risk management. Each WG consists of experts from science, policy and practice working in the field of WFRM. The members were “recruited” from the Firelogue sister projects as well as from the wider Firelogue Network.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, conflicts may have arisen due to competing or conflicting objectives and worldviews as well as differences in stakeholder views of what is fair, i.e., distributive, restorative and procedural justice. The issues were identified, explored and debated in the five Working Groups as depicted below.

3.2.2.2. Workshops. The aim of the implementation of Working Groups (WGs) in Firelogue was a detailed understanding of the implications of new WFRM measures from a multi-stakeholder perspective. More specifically, innovative approaches and measures as developed by the Innovation Actions (IAs) and FirEURisk were systematically collected and summarized in a first step. In a second step, their implications were discussed *within* the relevant WGs and as well as *between* the WGs to identify their alignment or contradiction with different stakeholder objectives and resulting synergies or potential conflicts. Finally, these insights aimed to build the basis for the development of consistent WFRM suggestions that take different stakeholder perspectives into consideration, and align them to the extent possible while specifying potential conflicts that need to be overcome.

Overall, the workshop design was co-created with the WG leaders. They defined an initial list of relevant topics, were actively involved in the set-up of the WGs in terms of participants and co-designed the workshop agenda in several iterations.

Building on the suggested relevant multi-stakeholder topics per WG, two hybrid workshops were implemented: one in July 2023 in Solsona, Spain and another one in April 2024 in Nea Makri, Greece. Both workshops lasted three days.

The **first day** included a field trip with initial input and room for discussions on the ground. In Spain for example, the first trip was made on Day 1 to the Natural Park of Montserrat (see Fig. 3), where participants were introduced to how the Fire Shepherds program⁷ operated and how their work helped enhance biodiversity and promote bio-economy. By emphasizing an innovative approach to traditional measures like prescribed burnings or grazing by goats and sheep, participants had the opportunity to observe how the project was working actively toward reducing the fuel loads in Catalanian forests in a sustainable way. In Greece, several stops related to the devastating fires in Mati in 2018 were made, including the origin of the fire, the boat evacuation sites and the (voluntary) fire services.

The **second day** was dedicated to the discussion in the respective Working Groups. WG leads were asked to develop two broad ideas of topics to discuss with their WG participants. The intention behind giving some topic suggestions to the WG participants was to avoid too generic and unfocused discussion during the workshop. The topics were chosen to be open enough to allow for a variety of ideas and viewpoints and incorporated some opportunities to overlap with other WGs.

The **third day** was dedicated to the cross-WG discussion with the aim to enrich the first day discussion with perspectives from other WGs. Participants were therefore mixed ensuring that each WG was represented in one of the five cross-WG groups. The WG leads presented the results of days and subsequently continued to work with one cross-WG group each.

The workshops clearly managed to reveal existing challenges but also opportunities and conflicts as well as innovations in managing wildfire risk and the multi-stakeholder relevance of most of these topics.

3.3. Comparative summary of the projects' co-creation goals and approaches

Main goals of the co-creation approach in RiskPACC have been to engage citizens in DRR; enhance two-way communication between citizens and CPAs; and develop solutions that consider the needs of all relevant stakeholders and groups that are supposed to benefit from the solutions, including marginalized and vulnerable groups. This was pursued by developing a tailored methodology that included the initialization of a workshop series in the RiskPACC case studies, (1) targeting an exchange of knowledge and perspectives, and (2) co-develop, test and refine dedicated tools.

Likewise, the main goals of the co-creation approach in Firelogue were to engage relevant stakeholders in the development of integrated WFRM strategies; enhance (mutual) understanding of stakeholder perspectives and needs; and consider justice aspects in WFRM strategies. This was pursued by establishing topic related working groups and conducting workshops. The workshops included (1) a joint field trip to pave the ground, (2) discussions within the working groups, and (3) cross-working group discussions.

4. Opportunities and challenges of co-creation in research projects

In this chapter, we reflect on opportunities (chapter 4.1) and challenges (chapter 4.2) from literature with the perspective of our experience in RiskPACC and Firelogue, and complement the results with additional insights and conclusions derived from applying co-

⁷ <https://www.fireshepherds.eu/>(19.09.2023).

Fig. 2. Firelogue approach to discussing justice implications of WFRM measures from different stakeholder perspectives.

Fig. 3. Discussions during the field trip of Day one at the Foothills of the Natural Park of Montserrat.

creation in the two projects (chapter 4.3).

4.1. Opportunities of co-creation in research projects

Opportunities of co-creation in research projects are mainly seen in:

- fostering a mutual understanding among diverse stakeholders,
- matching needs with possible solutions, and in
- considering the needs of the whole spectrum of relevant stakeholders in the process.

4.1.1. Enhance (mutual) understanding, learn from each other

4.1.1.1. *Description.* Enhanced mutual understanding among the different participating stakeholders can be seen as an enabler for the actual co-creation. E.g Fitzpatrick et al. [6] found that “social relations of research production that provide the structures within which all co-created knowledge is generated are more important drivers of effective knowledge mobilisation and implementation” [6, p. 1738].

Among others, co-creation can enhance the mutual understanding of researchers and practitioners (e.g. [6,50]), and support balancing an “academic ideal” with “local, contextual and solutions-focused approaches” [6, p. 1744].

4.1.1.2. *Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue.* In RiskPACC, an enhanced understanding among civil protection authorities and

citizens has been a major goal in the project. The social relations – e. g., between the case study partners, technology providers, local CPAs, citizens, etc. – have been the focal point. One main project goal was to mitigate the communication gap between these stakeholders. The co-creation workshops in the case studies of the project enabled discussions on eye-level to enhance mutual understanding and establish trust. The modular co-creation workshop process has been adapted from the academic research sphere, however, has been set up as modular and adaptable to the project partners’ – especially practitioners’ – needs.

In Firelogue, an enhanced understanding among different stakeholder groups in wildfire management has been a major goal in the project. New, multi-disciplinary networks were created that can facilitate the future exchange. The co-creation workshops in Firelogue served to understand the perspectives and needs of other stakeholder groups and the implications that certain measures or solutions may have for them. More specifically, the added value in Firelogue was created through the cross-fertilization of groups. In addition to the discussions inside the WGs, participants were mixed. Representatives summarized the discussions during the first round of the workshops. This allowed participants to get insights about the other WG discussions and to liaise their suggestions and their implications to these stakeholders. A range of additional aspects and things to consider were discussed during the workshop which clearly enriched the discussions inside the WGs.

The getting together of stakeholders also broadened their networks, which can in turn enhance mutual understanding in the future (see also chapter 4.3.4).

4.1.2. Match solutions with actual needs

4.1.2.1. Description. By involving the users in the development of what is co-created (e.g. a tool, a methodology, a policy or a strategy), matching the outcome with actual needs is possible (e.g. [1,6]). Co-creation facilitates revealing the specific needs, identifying possible solutions or functionalities, as well as context factors to be considered, but also setting (research) priorities (e.g. [51]). In addition, through close collaboration of practice and research, the transfer of scientific results into practical application is facilitated, increasing impact, practical value and efficiency of research (e.g. [6,52]).

4.1.2.2. Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue. In RiskPACC, possible functionalities of software tools and case studies’ specific needs were matched, and tools were only further co-developed in case studies where they were deemed useful for addressing the case study specific issues. Thus, the co-creation approach facilitated setting priorities for (co-)developing solutions. There has been an ongoing exchange of data and information between the project partners, i.e., the researchers, technology providers, case study owners, as well as the workshop participants (including citizens, CPA representatives), and additional stakeholders. The project partners agreed in the pursuit to transfer collaboratively developed ideas and solutions into real practice and/or real practical solutions, e.g., the project’s ICTs. As part of citizen science, the co-creation workshops aim to connect diverse bodies and make for an efficient and effective exchange.

In Firelogue, strategies and policy recommendations matching the actual practical needs were targeted. Research and practical aims were aligned when co-developing policy suggestions. The transfer of scientific outputs into practice was facilitated through jointly identifying justice aspects in WFRM and the development of recommendations. Ensuring impact and increasing efficiency were main ideas of exploring the co-creation of WFRM strategies. Firelogue experimented with formats to establish this and to draft suggestions for enhancing WFRM at the European scale. The co-creation approach allowed to identify priorities for action.

4.1.3. Consider the needs of the whole spectrum of relevant stakeholders

4.1.3.1. Description. Another most relevant opportunity of co-creation is that the whole spectrum of relevant stakeholders is involved in the development of solutions, methodologies, policies or strategies, which are supposed to represent the interests of each of them. This can concern representatives of academia/universities, industry, state/government, and civil society, according to the “Quadruple Helix Model” for fostering innovation [25,26]. The most relevant stakeholders differ from case to case, while it is specifically important to consider marginalized groups (e.g. [6]). To successfully characterize the involvement of relevant stakeholders [53,54], also clarify that the stakeholders should “participate in the design, implementation and operation of the assessment” [53] in [54, p. 348].

4.1.3.2. Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue. In RiskPACC, especially civil protection authorities and citizen groups including marginalized or vulnerable groups were targeted participants, complemented by research and technology providers. The more specific definition of relevant stakeholders varied among the case studies and included, for example, teachers in one case study, volunteers in a second case study, firefighters in a third case study. The involvement of all stakeholders across all stages has not fully been the case in RiskPACC, as some stakeholder groups, e.g. citizens, have by nature not participated in the design of the co-creation activity, or in each case study, or the project itself beyond the workshops.

In Firelogue, multi-stakeholder involvement in the WFRM domain has been pursued. It is an important matter of justice trying to include all perspectives and also necessary to create effective solutions, policies and strategies. For WFRM, discussions on the questions of who is actually part of the wildfire risk management community are ongoing and might be responded differently depending on context and mandate. As far as the WFRM Innovation Actions funded under the EU Green Deal are concerned, the approaches for each project were analysed and integrated. The analysis resulted in the following list of key actors [55]:

- **Emergency management organizations**, e.g., firefighters, civil protection, medical services and police, first responders performing operations in the field, fire analysts, forest services.
- **Scientific community**, e.g., research and academic institutions involved in diverse scientific areas related to wildfire management, fire safety engineers, forest services.
- **Policy making bodies**, e.g., administrations acting at different territorial levels, EU law and policymakers, national and local politicians.
- **Land management groups**, e.g., landowner associations, land planners, farmers, foresters, whose activity has direct implications over fuel load management through burning, cutting, grazing and other activities.
- **Environmental associations**, e.g., conservation organizations, environmental consultancies, environmental educators.
- **Media**, e.g., journalists, communicators in the environmental field; social media influencers.
- **Society**, e.g., social groups, volunteer associations, representatives for certain citizen groups, vulnerable groups.
- **Industry, technology, and innovation**, e.g., the industry around sectors of energy, construction, infrastructures, timber, technologies, fire prevention and firefighting equipment; Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance industry.

4.2. Challenges of co-creation in research projects

Challenges of co-creation in research projects are mainly seen in:

- mutual understanding, terminology, and language,
- time and resources,
- (continuous) involvement of all relevant stakeholders,
- equitable distribution of power to justly recognize different interests, and
- required skills in co-creation.

4.2.1. Mutual understanding, terminology, and language

4.2.1.1. Description. The diversity of stakeholders participating in a co-creation process can lead to challenges regarding mutual understanding, common terminology, and language. While increasing mutual understanding is a major goal and opportunity of co-creation (see chapter 4.1), it can also present a challenge within the process itself and requires proper attention, which includes the choice of appropriate approaches and methods [1]. If not properly addressed, a lack of understanding can lead to conflict and hinder the co-creation process [56,57]. While co-creation brings together knowledge and perspectives of different local stakeholders, or “local knowledges”, these differences, possibly in combination with unequal power distribution (s. b.), can also lead to conflict if not rightly considered [58]. Next to tensions among local players, another possible tension demanding attention is the one between science and practice, researchers and practitioners/citizens. This concerns speaking different languages, both figuratively and literally, but also priorities in terms of scientific validity versus practical and solution focused strategies [1,6]. Again, enhancing this mutual understanding between research and practice is an opportunity of co-creation, but requires attention during the process, in order to avoid failure of the co-creation process.

4.2.1.2. Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue. In RiskPACC, various types of stakeholders (citizens, volunteers, volunteer and civil protection organization representatives, technology providers and research organization representatives) from multiple European countries have been involved, enforcing the relevance of mutual understanding. Language played a major role, since workshops were conducted in different countries on local level, involving local people but also project partners from multiple countries. Not all local participants spoke English fluently, and project partners did not all speak the local languages. To address this, project material was translated into local languages, and vice versa, outcomes of co-creation workshops were translated back to English. In addition, technical tools that were tested and further co-developed in the case studies were initially only developed in English. Due to the language barrier, some of these tools were developed in case study languages as well (e. g., the AEOLIAN App, see chapter 3.1.2, was translated to Greek and Hebrew).

In contrast, thanks to the different approach in Firelogue, focusing on multi-stakeholder exchange rather than local case studies, the language barrier was not a big issue. Working groups were formed of international experts and discussions could be held in English. However, the issue of using different terminologies appeared in Firelogue, too, being a re-occurring topic in interdisciplinary research projects. To address this, project partners worked with scenarios and input documents as well as field trips (s. a.) in order to pave the grounds.

Another challenge regarding mutual understanding was experienced in Firelogue due to the complexity of the methodological set-up. It was not trivial for everybody to understand, especially the cross-fertilization aspect, of which the added-value was only realized after the workshops by many participants. In RiskPACC, the modular set-up may have appeared complex at first, however, once the process was understood and the right methodologies were picked, the complexity was reduced during these adaptations. Regarding possible tensions between science and practice, both projects made sure to leave sufficient room during the process to reveal possible conflicts and identify obstacles towards practical implementation of research results.

The Participatory Mapping approach (see chapter 3.1) in RiskPACC, for example, was considered a suitable approach for enhancing

mutual understanding, since participants discussed about the same (geographically located) topics from their different perspectives. The Risk communication exercise (ibid.) also revealed different understandings and perspectives, which were then able to be addressed.

4.2.2. Time and resources

4.2.2.1. *Description.* Proper participation in co-creation requires time and resources, which, if limited, can risk the effectiveness of the overall collaboration and co-creation process [1,6,59,60]. Thus, funding conditions are crucial, which ideally cover the whole duration of the co-creation process. Sufficient time is, amongst others, crucial for the required trust-building as a basis for co-creation [6], and for properly ensuring the transfer of research results (which are usually ready only by the end of a project) into practice [50].

4.2.2.2. *Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue.* In RiskPACC, main parts of the co-creation work were covered by project funds. One of the main goals was to establish a trustful relationship through ongoing exchange between citizens and Civil Protection Authorities that would ideally extend over the project lifetime and be a self-runner. However, participation in the co-creation workshops beyond the project partners was not funded and dependent on voluntary commitments. Expenses of external participants could not be reimbursed, plus, availability during a week day was required, which limited the participation of interested candidates. The “Continuation” phase of the co-creation process in RiskPACC (see chapter 3.1) may not be realized after the project has ended, because partners cannot be expected to keep the workshops (or tools) running with no funds.

This challenge is reinforced by the duration of co-creation workshops that is required to achieve effective results. In Firelogue, proper implementation required time, including workshops lasting three full days. This challenged the participation of the required multi-disciplinary stakeholders in terms of their availability but also in terms of budgetary constraints with respect to the travel costs that could be covered. Thus, time and resources essentially influenced which stakeholders could actually be activated. The workshops in RiskPACC lasted about one day, but due to the iterative component, several workshops were conducted in each case study.

4.2.3. Continuous involvement of all relevant stakeholder groups

4.2.3.1. *Description.* Closely related to the challenges of time and resources is the challenge of involving all relevant stakeholder groups, continuously along the whole co-creation process. Stakeholders, especially those that do not receive funding, may join and leave the process at different stages [1]. Missing incentives prevent a stronger commitment for enhancing the science-practice connection [50]. However, for building trust, and an equitable distribution of power (see 4.2.4), it is required to involve stakeholders in the long term [6].

4.2.3.2. *Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue.* In RiskPACC, long term involvement was required because methods, tools, and technological solutions have been iteratively refined over time. However, also in RiskPACC, co-creation was understood as a process that can be set up at any stage of development, meaning that solutions or concepts may not be ideated from scratch, yet developed further (see chapter 3.1.2). This was important to match requirements of the project’s proposal that already requested initial suggestions of possible solutions. However, as mentioned above, especially the “Continuation” phase of the co-creation process can be at risk if not funded accordingly.

Next to the challenge of continuous involvement, the aim of involving “all” relevant stakeholders can be challenging. Ideally, all stakeholders that have a say in the specific context are represented in the co-creation process. For RiskPACC, the question of representativeness in co-creation workshops was highly relevant, as the project’s co-creation and collaborative governance approaches have been nourished by core values such as representativeness. (Vulnerable) groups have been represented directly, or, if suitable and possible, they were represented by others (e. g., students’ interests or experience with DRR represented by their teachers). A “full” representation was often not reached also due to limitations such as budget and time. However, the workshop methodology asked for workshops being open and accessible to all relevant groups. In some cases, where specific groups were identified but not represented, their (assumed) needs were still considered in solution development.

For Firelogue, too, stakeholders that could actually be activated strongly depended on resources availability, time, and interest. In addition, aspects of representativeness were considered in the selection process. The wide geographic coverage and complexity of the topics made it impossible to actually involve all relevant stakeholders. During the exploratory workshops, only a very limited number of individuals could participate. The views included are thus selective even though geographic coverage, technical expertise and gender aspects were monitored.

Chapter 4.3.1 further elaborates on the challenge of representativeness in the context of EU projects.

4.2.4. Equitable distribution of power to justly recognize different interests

4.2.4.1. *Description.* A prerequisite for effective co-creation is that the diverse stakeholders have an equal voice (s. a.), and that power distributions among stakeholders are balanced [1,6,61]. This was pursued by the workshop methodologies in both projects. A collaboration of diverse stakeholders can also bring challenges regarding different interests and priorities [6], for example, between researchers following their interest to broaden scientific knowledge and practitioners looking for practically implementable solutions within their specific context [50]. Then, strong moderation and communication can guide the focus on the common interests and goals,

addressing the needs of both sides.

4.2.4.2. Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue. In RiskPACC, an equal say of participants was highly relevant to the whole process throughout all project stages; core values of co-creation may only be realized if the traditional top-down approaches are supplemented by representative bottom-up channels. It is the other side of the coin to a successful involvement of all relevant stakeholders, to first identify those groups and include them in the co-creation process. In RiskPACC, the project conducted more than 20 co-creation workshops in six case study areas. The stakeholders included in the workshops have been very specific to the respective case study, but they have been defined before the workshop took place in internal processes in order to invite them as participants. The challenge concerning diverse stakeholders with different interests became apparent in two ways. *Firstly*, all the identified stakeholders were invited to the workshops, including representatives of groups that could not attend themselves (e. g., young pupils) and/or were marginalized. The case study partners made strong efforts in order to involve them, for example through repetitive invitations to the female workforce in DRR, such as successfully shown by reaching female firefighters in the Czech case study. This has however not always been successful, as the team has not been able to include equal distributions of male and female firefighters, for example, in the workshops in the German case study. Such imbalances oftentimes stem from unequal distributions in the group sourced; for example, in DRR the workforce is still male dominated. *Secondly*, the diverse stakeholders with their different interests should be enabled to share their perspectives without limit due to former power imbalances (e. g. experts vs. lay people due to their relation and/or profession in DRR). Setting the stage at the co-creation workshops for ensuring that all participants have an equal voice (s. chapter 3.1.1), was one way for the workshop organizers to support this. However, not all power imbalances can be tackled in the course of a co-creation activity or project.

The top-down/bottom-up tension was not a focus in Firelogue, and a good gender balance and also geographic distribution of experts could be achieved. However, the project was concerned with ensuring that all participants would have an equal voice in the workshops. Quite naturally, some individuals are more vocal than others and hence, results could be biased towards individual opinions. Firelogue hence combined individual work phases in which the participants noted their thoughts and reflections on cards with oral phases in which each participant presented the thoughts and discussed them. The documentation was then based on both, the written and oral contributions.

4.2.5. Competencies, skills in co-creation

4.2.5.1. Description. It has further been noted that competencies and skills in co-creation practices can essentially influence the results of the co-creation process [1]. Co-creation depends on the diverse skillset of the process. The methodology can appear rather complex, which needs to be addressed properly. In addition, the participants need to have an equal say (s. a.), which needs to be ensured by the facilitators. Facilitators need to understand and properly execute the co-creation methodology, and for properly processing and making sense of the data and results of the workshop, skills of the project partners (researchers, technology providers etc.) can be of high relevance.

4.2.5.2. Relevance in RiskPACC and Firelogue. This is also true for the two projects. In RiskPACC, the success of co-creation depended on the diverse skillset of project partners implementing the process. “Train the moderator” workshops were conducted to enable case study owners to properly implement the co-creation workshops. They had to properly communicate the complex methodology, invite the right people, make sure that participants have an equal voice, and process the results of the workshop in line with the project’s objectives.

In Firelogue, the methodology applied in the workshops appeared rather complex since it was formed of several rounds of discussions, first inside the thematic groups and cross-connecting them in a second step. The facilitators were hence informed in an encompassing way prior to the workshop and a dedicated handbook with templates was developed to guide the implementations.

4.3. Additional specific insights from RiskPACC and Firelogue

In this chapter, we describe additional insights, especially specific opportunities and challenges resulting from pertinent characteristics of multi-country research projects, as experienced during the implementation of RiskPACC and Firelogue.

4.3.1. Representativeness of participants in co-creation activities in EU projects

In the context of continuous involvement of relevant stakeholders (chapter 4.2.3), the challenge of representativeness has been mentioned. We recognize specific challenges of representativeness in co-creation workshops in an EU project setup:

Representativeness was the key challenge in the implementation of the Firelogue co-creation approach. As depicted, WFRM is a very complex topic that requires the engagement of a diverse range of relevant stakeholders. In addition, wildfire risk realities largely differ across Europe which again should have been considered in the selection of Working Group and workshop participants despite general aspects such as gender and vulnerable groups. These aspects are even more important as matters of procedural justice were pointed out by the Firelogue framework.

However, organizational factors limited the actual number of participants which are depicted in the following. Firstly, Firelogue as a Coordination and Support Action for the Green Deal Wildfire Risk Management projects was mandated to integrate these projects’ partners and results and hence had to draw on that selective pool preliminary while in a second step, Working Group leaders’ networks

were activated to increase diversity of WG participants. Secondly, two workshops were implemented, covering the costs for participants. However, in terms of budgetary and logistic limitations, only up to ten participants could be covered per Working Group resulting in about 50 physical participants per workshop. The participants were thereby balanced in terms of gender and geographic representation and covering different profiles from infrastructure providers to first responders, insurers and foresters. Nevertheless, their contributions still had to be regarded as context specific and the results could hence not be representative.

The challenge of representativeness was addressed in two main ways. On the one hand, the processes and contributing individuals and organizations were explicitly mentioned - to the extent that data protection regulations allowed for it - so that the initial policy recommendation development process became transparent. Secondly, the project structure foresaw several feed-back processes, presenting the initial set of suggestions in workshops with the European Commission and a large networking event with all concerned projects among others. During these events, opportunities for feedback were built in and led to a specification and adaptation. However, only English-speaking participants already connected to an international network of experts participated in the events which again limited the representativeness. Hence, in a final round of feedback, specific organisations that were not yet represented will be identified by the project stakeholder manager and be contacted bilaterally for comments.

Challenges in representativeness in RiskPACC have been described as well in chapter 4.2.3; reaching representativeness proved to be one of the core challenges in RiskPACC from the researchers' and practitioners' points of view. Issues related to the EU project context are seen in a limited reimbursement for participants, and the varying targeted stakeholder/participant groups among the case studies, which both hampered the representativeness of participants co-creation workshops in RiskPACC.

4.3.2. Co-creating from scratch? Development stages of (co-created) technological solutions

In the process of co-creation, especially in the cases where technological solutions were to be co-created, there was a discussion around whether the further development of the previously chosen technological tools was an exhaustive co-creation process, looking at the starting point of picking up the creation and design of a technological tool.

As the four technological solutions that have been part of the RiskPACC project did already exist on TRL 2 or higher (s. chapter 3.1.2), it can be noted that the tools and its functionalities had not been co-created *from scratch*. However, the project showed that developing four pre-existing technologies further and adapting them to realistic needs of the local particularities of the case studies they have been tested in, still constituted a co-creational process.

In this context, it shall be noted that design thinking and co-creation processes can be applied to be able to make technological innovations more disruptive, which is needed to make inventions sustainable, scalable, and replicable [62]. Design thinking processes are iterative processes of invention. Having a look at the phases of infinite and ongoing phases of innovation, one can see that innovations have always been building on inventions of the past. Innovations appear to have different levels of development, and a process of design thinking can be adapted at every stage (see Fig. 4). Innovations always build on inventions made before, otherwise there would be no (technological) progress. Therefore, we argue that in the infinite process of innovations, with one innovation building up on past inventions, such a process never starts 'from scratch', but instead should be considered as a process of developing something *further*.

As a result, we consider the co-design and co-development of the RiskPACC technological tools a fully-fledged adaption of co-creation. Co-creation can be applied both at all stages of (technological) development (e. g., TRLs) to develop something *further*, and also show different levels of citizen participation, as seen in the work of Arnstein [18] and discussed above. The co-creation workshops can be considered artifacts [28], making them state-of-the-art adaptations to their environment with a somewhat experimental set-up. The technological tools developed in RiskPACC's co-creation workshops work with past inventions to make progress, both in the sense of technological development, as much as aiming at enhancing citizen and stakeholder participation.

4.3.3. Readiness level of co-created solutions

Very much related to the development stages of solutions is the readiness level of solutions by the end of the project, which determines the possibility to be implemented directly after the project. The requested targeted TRLs of EU projects differ, but often lower TRLs are expected, far below market-readiness.

While there may be good reasons for lower TRLs, they can contribute to what is often called the "valley of death", i.e. the gap between project results and their actual implementation. For the co-creation approach, the challenge is two-fold: Firstly, the co-creation approaches as developed in the projects, leading to established structures, networks, strategies and methods, are at risk to disappear after the projects' end. This refers to the "Continuation" phase in RiskPACC. Secondly, the co-developed (technological) solutions, if not market-ready, are at risk to be not developed further, or very much depend on individual exploitation, options and activities. The challenge of lacking applicable solutions by the end of the project lifetime determines the interest of potential stakeholders in participating in the co-creation process and is hence interlinked with representativeness (s.a.).

4.3.4. Networking and establishing relationships

We described challenges related to a mutual understanding, terminology and language, resulting from diversity in disciplines, stakeholder groups, languages, or experiences (chapter 4.1.1). These challenges can gain relevance in a multi-country context. However, we experienced in both projects that once these challenges were overcome, many participants very much appreciated that they were able to connect with relevant people and stakeholders, learned about perspectives they were not aware of before, and established useful relationships. In Firelogue, it was most relevant to get to know participants from other stakeholder groups to exchange views and expertise beyond the scope of the workshop. In RiskPACC, the six case study regions that conducted the co-creation workshops have been advised to continue the exchange so that citizens and CPAs are given the chance to establish and improve these

Fig. 4. Applying Design Thinking to the infinite process of Innovation⁸¹.

networks and relationships.

5. Discussion & conclusion

Reflecting on our leading question (*a*) *In how far were the opportunities and challenges identified in previous studies confirmed in RiskPACC and Firelogue? In what way do they differ?*, the following can be summarized and derived from the description of opportunities and challenges (chapters 4.1 and 4.2).

5.1. Opportunities

The opportunity of *fostering a mutual understanding among diverse stakeholders* was surely confirmed in both projects. One of the main objectives in the RiskPACC project was specifically to enhance mutual understanding between CPAs and citizens, which means that the co-creation approach itself directly contributed to reaching this objective, i.e. by applying the approach during the project, by establishing respective methods and strategies for future co-creation activities, and by co-creating several (technological and non-technological) solutions that support mutual understanding. Similarly, in Firelogue, enhancing understanding among different stakeholder groups in wildfire management has been a major objective.

Matching needs with possible solutions was confirmed to be an opportunity of co-creation in the projects, too. In RiskPACC, this became specifically obvious when matching case studies' needs with possible functionalities of technological solutions. In Firelogue, strategies and policy recommendations matching the actual practical needs were targeted.

Considering the needs of the whole spectrum of relevant stakeholders in the process was a requirement in both projects as well. In RiskPACC, it was, for example important to consider the specific needs of vulnerable groups. In Firelogue, it was most relevant because considering all perspectives is an important matter of justice. However, while in Firelogue the stakeholder groups were the same across the project, in RiskPACC they differed among the case studies, so that a holistic and detailed list of relevant stakeholders was impossible. Thus, the identification of stakeholders to be involved in the co-creation approach very much depends on the project set-up. This is especially true when solutions are targeted that are useable across countries, different hazard types and in different social or cultural contexts. To create all activities and assessments with all stakeholder groups from scratch appears as an aspiration yet to achieve. In both projects, this highest form of involvement has not been achievable due to the composition of the project itself and its activities.

5.2. Challenges

The challenges concerning *mutual understanding, terminology, and language*, became specifically obvious, first, in context of language issues: co-creation workshops were conducted in RiskPACC with local stakeholders, often non-English speakers, while involving project partners from different countries. Some solutions could only be developed in English, with limited translation possibilities. Second, hurdles in terminology appeared in both projects, which, however, seems to be common in interdisciplinary projects/activities, and not specific to co-creation. Third, complex methodologies can lead to misunderstanding and conflict. To address the challenge of language in co-creation approaches in multi-country research projects, it seems useful to plan in respective translation needs, both for the co-creation activities as well as for the co-created solutions, depending on the specific target. To overcome terminology issues, activities in the beginning to pave the ground proved useful, including the integration of scenarios and joint field trips. Further dedicated workshop methodologies (such as participatory mapping) can strengthen mutual understanding.

The challenges of *time and resources* came up in the projects, too, especially related to missing resources after a project's end, as well as limited capacities of participants that are not reimbursed for their participation in co-creation activities. The challenges of time and resources underline the need for adequate funding mechanisms, effective political support and/or other incentives to motivate stakeholders to participate in co-creation approaches.

The *(continuous) involvement of all relevant stakeholders* is challenged by the described issues of time and resources, as well as by the

aim of representativeness, which can be specifically challenging in EU projects involving multiple countries. Thus, also here, adequate funding mechanisms and/or other incentives are indispensable, and the restraints in representativeness should be properly considered already in the design of the co-creation approach, identification of stakeholders and participants, but also in the assessment and evaluation of results.

Challenges of *equitable distribution of power to justly recognize different interests*, appeared in the projects, while they seem to be not uniquely related to EU projects. General measures to ensure equal voices, detect and reflect imbalances in power, and identify and address different interests shall be put in place to fulfil the requirements of equitable distribution of power, and justly recognizing different interests in co-creation.

Required skills in co-creation, too, were needed in the projects but seem not uniquely related to EU projects. The recognized challenges were, for example addressed by “train the trainer” sessions, which proved a suitable approach in RiskPACC. Proper attention to ensuring that leaders of co-creation activities have the required skills is important for the success of co-creation, which includes the enforcement of equal voices among participants.

For our second leading question, (b) *What are additional insights from applying co-creation approaches in RiskPACC and Firelogue? In how far are they related to characteristics of EU research projects involving multiple countries?*, we derived the topics as elaborated in chapter 4.3:

The general challenge of *representativeness of participants in co-creation activities* can be multiplied in the context of EU projects involving multiple countries. Research topics can require a diversity of stakeholders to be involved, and different context conditions in different countries and/or case studies may even multiply the number of required stakeholders. As mentioned, the design of the co-creation approach, identification of stakeholders and participants, but also the assessment and evaluation of results should properly reflect this.

An issue that came up specifically in RiskPACC was related to *development stages of co-created technological solutions*, and the question if one can claim that co-creation actually took place if the solution was not co-developed *from scratch*. We find that developing pre-existing technologies further and adapting them to realistic needs still constitutes a co-creational process.

Closely connected to this is the *readiness level of co-created solutions*, which is often clearly defined in the form of expected TRL in EU projects, and are often far below market-readiness, which challenges the continuation and further implementation of co-creation (and the co-developed solutions) after a project’s end. The restricted possibilities to continue the work or implement results coming out of a project have of course been recognized earlier, e.g. Ref. [50]. Respective recommendations (see e.g. Ref. [65]) and approaches (e.g. initiatives of the European Commission such as the “Booster”, which offers services to EU-funded projects supporting dissemination and exploitation⁹) to fill this gap exist, and need to be strengthened and further implemented.

After overcoming described challenges in the two projects, many participants very much welcomed the *networking experience* in the co-creation activities and that they were able to establish useful relationships. This opportunity seems to be true beyond EU projects, while multi-country involvement may multiply this experience.

5.3. Concluding remarks

Co-creation approaches in research projects can essentially enrich science in DRR, and especially the science-practice connection. It can facilitate mutual understanding among diverse stakeholders, match research and solution developments to actual needs, and involve all relevant stakeholders, especially those that are, in traditional approaches, only passive receivers of innovations, where their interests and perspectives may either be ignored or only considered by educated guess.

Co-creation approaches can significantly differ, also depending on “what” is actually co-created, i.e. a technical product, a methodology, a strategy, or policy recommendations. The expected TRL, for example, influenced the co-development in RiskPACC, but not in Firelogue. However, some common challenges exist.

We cannot claim that our observations in RiskPACC and Firelogue are generally true for EU research projects involving multiple countries. Some of our experiences however show clear relations to characteristics of such projects: Language issues can be related to the involvement of stakeholders from different countries as well as the ambition to develop solutions that work on local level in different countries. The number of stakeholders to be involved may increase, too, when involving several countries. Issues of time and resources very much depend on funding requirements. Challenges of representativeness can be exacerbated when trying to involve a large number of stakeholder groups in several countries.

Despite these challenges, the projects were able to show that co-creating solutions to enhance disaster risk reduction, via EU research projects involving multiple countries, provide unique opportunities for developing suitable and practicably implementable solutions. They facilitate relationships of diverse stakeholders and the required involvement of citizens including the most vulnerable.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maïke Vollmer: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Claudia Berchtold:** Writing – original draft. **Jeannette Anniés:** Writing – original draft.

⁹ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/> (accessed 23/12/2024).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Maike Vollmer reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Claudia Berchtold reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Jeannette Annies reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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